

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**HOW MANY PATIENTS IN HOSPITALS AND DIFFERENT
WARDS WERE SATISFIED IN CASE OF FACILITIES GIVEN
THEM BY AB HEALTH CARE CENTERS**¹Dr Ziaullah, ¹Dr Rezaullah, ²Allah Nawaz¹Medical Officer Kunar Provincial Hospital, Afghanistan, ²RHC Fort Marot Bahawalnagar.**Article Received:** February 2019**Accepted:** March 2019**Published:** April 2019**Abstract:**

Background: Health care ratio is different in different region of the world. The facilities provided by a hospital can be noticed by the satisfaction of patients. The first achievement of any health care center is to satisfy the patients.

Objectives: The main objectives of this study was to find out that how many patients in hospitals and different wards were satisfied in case of facilities given them by ab health care centers.

Subjects and Methods: This study was explanatory consisting of 1535 patients. They were questioned about their visit, reason for this visit, about registration, and their ideas about doctor's attitudes and behavior of other staff. The information was collected by the different patients from different wards and departments. SPSS version 15 was used to enter and examine the data.

Results: The study contained that 1535 patients from different departments wards. The data that was collected about either the patients were educated or not. Either the patients are married or unmarried. The data about occupation of patients was also collected. It was also asked by the patients that which type of visit they were doing. Out of total patients 52% were males, 72% married. It was noted that registration corner was overfilled, it was told by 73% were married. It was noticed that registration corner was overfilled, it was told by 73% patients. 84% patients were uneducated and only 10% were educated. Most of the patients showed satisfaction on the facilities they were provided as well as on the attitude of doctors and other members of hospital.

Conclusion: The study showed the satisfaction of most of the patients in case of doctor's action and time given by the doctors to the patients. Most of the patients were uneducated, married and unemployed. Most of the patients told that registration corner was over filled. They did not find any difficulty during searching the desiring departments.

Keywords: Patient satisfaction, Tertiary care hospital, Doctors.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Ziaullah,**

Medical Officer Kunar Provincial Hospital, Afghanistan

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ziaullah et al., *How Many Patients in Hospitals and Different Wards Were Satisfied In Case Of Facilities Given Them by Ab Health Care Centers.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(04).

INTRODUCTION:

Patients satisfaction is the ratio between what the patients thought and what he/she got in case or health care [1]. Health care ratio is different in different regions of the world. The facilities provided by a hospital can be measured by the satisfaction of patients. The first achievement of any health care center is to satisfy the patients. Patients satisfaction is affected by clinical as well as non-clinical outcomes of care. That's why it is very complex to find out the patient's satisfaction [2]. A patient is main part of any health care center. The patients suffered by any stress or tension and that type of patients' needs more care treatment and good behaviors and case at hospital [3]. Patients satisfaction or dissatisfaction can be measured only when the patients visited the hospital and noticed the facilities given to them. It is very important to find out the ratio of patient's satisfaction because it may be helpful in case to provide better health care facilities. Satisfaction of patient is not taken as an important factor in developing countries [4]. Many factors affect the patient's satisfaction such as which type of facilities are given to the patients. Either medicines are available or not. How doctors behave to the patient's satisfaction [5]. Now a day, patients are less satisfied need better facilities in case of health in contrast to past patients. Which type of facilities are given to the patients and how these are effectives, it can be measured by patient's satisfaction [6]. Quality of health care can be measured by patient's response and it is very important to measures it health facilities can only be improved by patient's response [7]. Dissatisfaction occurs when patients thought more but gain much less than it [8]. Due to patient's satisfaction any health center can give better facilities to the patients according to their desire [9]. Problems in health can only be noticed by patient's response. Patients satisfaction or response provide a guide line to solve the health problems. Patients perception and cultures can be changed by developing a natural interest by the response of patients [10]. Satisfaction of patients play an important role to make health care center more comfortable and attractive for patients.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS:

The study was explanatory and cross-sectional. The study was organized in Mayo Hospital Lahore. The duration of this study was from 1st August 2017 to 31st Nov, 2018. The study contained the 1535 patients from different department and from different wards. Most of the patients were males bit it also included females. The average age of this study was from 19 to 79 years. Some patients were suffered from disease badly. They were not able to answer the questions during the survey. The information about the study was collected by the guardians of patients. Performa was designed before adding the data that was collected during survey. The information was noted in Performa. Performa contained the different questions. The questions were about the age, education, gender, medical history. It was also asked about the behaviors of doctors and about case of hospital. Answer of these questioned were recorded in the study and before including the study, it was checked completed comprehensively. SPSS version 15 was used to record the data and the data was completely examined.

RESULTS:

The study contained the 1535 patients from different departments and wards. The data was collected about either the patients were educated or not. Either the patients are married or unmarried. The data about the occupation of patients was also collected. It was also asked by the patients which type of visit they were doing and from which department they were relating. 3 categories were made about the questions related to visit. They were as follow:

- 1: whether the patients were visiting it first time or
- 2: it was 2nd or 3rd visit after the advice of doctors and the patients visited the hospital before it.
- 3: it was visit by the appeal from any other hospital.

Out of total patients 52% were males, 71% were married. It was noted that the registration corner was over-filled, it was told by 73% patients 83% patients were uneducated and only 10% were educated. 45% patients were satisfied by the attitudes of doctors was as good as they wanted. 84% was satisfied by treatment of doctors. 89% was satisfied that doctors gave them proper time. 77% patients come to hospital for treatment and follow up cases were 22%.

Table I: Characteristics of patients (N=1535)

		Frequency	%age
Age (years)	<20	281	18
	20-29	276	17.98
	30-39	262	17.07
	40-49	352	22.93
	50-59	122	7.95
	60-69	179	11.66
	70-79	63	4.10
Gender			
	Males	807	52.57
	Females	728	47.43
Education			
	Illiterate	1287	83.84
	Matric	93	6.06
	Above Matric	155	10.10
Residence			
	Urban		
	Rural		
Marital status			
	Married	1104	71.92
	Unmarried	431	28.08
Occupation	Businessman	63	4.10
	shopkeeper	45	2.93
	Labor	317	20.65
	Employee	122	7.95
	House wife	633	41.24
	Student	141	9.19
	Farmer	135	8.79
	No	79	5.15
Problems in locating the department			
	Yes	383	24
	No	1152	75
Was registration counter overcrowded			
	Yes	1130	73
	No	405	26

Table II: Patients perception towards doctors

Behavior of the doctor?	
Good	750(48%)
satisfactory	697(45%)
poor	88(5%)
Patient perceives that time given by the doctor is adequate	
Adequate	1370(89%)
Inadequate	165(10%)
Patients come to hospital for?	
Followup	353(22%)
Treatment	1182(77%)
Have patient got checked by doctor	
Yes	1503((97%)
No	30(1%)
Patients checked by whom ?	
Medical Officer	867(56%)
Assistant Professor	342(22%)
Associate Professor	125(8%)
professor	201(13%)
Did doctor tell the patient about disease?	
Yes	1370(89%)
No	165(10%)
Did doctor tell the patient about treatment?	
Yes	1370(89%)
No	165(10%)
Are the patients satisfied by doctor?	
Yes	1318(85%)
No	217(14%)

DISCUSSION:

There are many goals to check out the patient's satisfaction. The three main causes to do so as follow:

1. Which type of health care facilities should be given to the patients, according to patients.
2. The study would help to find out the problems regarding the health.
3. This study would help to solve out the problems of health.

Patients only dissatisfied when they think more and find less and they find less. Patients satisfied about the health care when they think less and they find out more [12].

According to the study 93% were satisfied by the attitude of doctors. According to ARPITA Bhatta-Charya et al at 98.2% patients were satisfied with the attitude of doctors. These two figures were quite similar to each other. Another study was organized in India, this study showed that 94% patients find out the relative hospital easily and find no problem. 70% find out desiring departments within the hospitals. 80% patients told that registration corner was over filled. The attitude of registration clerk was cleared satisfied by the 63% patients. Most of the patients were agreed that they were given proper time by the doctors 77%, [13]

Most of the patient find out their desiring hospital and departments easily. Crow et al explained the reason of old aged people behavior towards satisfaction. The reason according to him was that the old aged people received more facilities in comparison they were thinking about. They were provided with more facilities than younger people. That explanatory study was organized to find out that how many patients were satisfied with health care provided in hospital in regional institute of medical science. It was organized during the month of May 2007. 260, 74.1% patients showed their satisfaction. Satisfaction towards the attitude of doctors and other employers of hospital at lower health facilities. They were quite unsatisfied in case of those facilities at higher level facilities. It is quite similar to our study [15]. Expert doctors were the main attraction for the patients to select the hospital. Most of the patients were agreed that they were given basic facilities and doctors showed their best attitude to the patients [16]. It was noted that 47% patients were children of age below 15 years in Pakistan. 56% were females of age about 26 years. 38 second were the average dispensing time 1.7 miles were taken by the consultation. The average number of drugs were 2.7. Out of these numbers 1.6 were being dispensed from the facility. More than half of the physician's recipe included antibiotic and patients about (15%)

were advised to take these drugs with injection. In this study, only half number of patients showed their satisfaction during the visit of hospital. It is quite different from our study because in our study more satisfaction was showed by the patients.

CONCLUSION:

This study revealed that action and behavior of the doctors impressed the patients greatly. Most of the uneducated married and women not doing any job outside were included in this study and they visited the hospital most of the patients not suffered from any difficulty during searching the targeted department, even though there was a large assembly of patients at registration corner. After checking the quality of care and satisfaction of patients, the quality of hospital and care centers can be improved.

REFERENCES:

1. Prahlad Rai Sodani, Rajeev K Kumar, Jayati Srivastava Laxman Sharma. Measuring Patient Satisfaction: A Case Study to Improve Quality of Care at Public Health Facilities. *Indian J Com Med* 2010 Jan; 35(1): 52-56.
2. Arshad S, Andrabi H, Hamid, Shamila, Masooda S. Measuring patients satisfaction: a cross sectional study to improve quality of care at a tertiary care hospital. *East Afr J Public Health* 2012 Mar; 9(1):26-8.
3. Hafeez, A. G. Kiani, S. ud Din, W. Muhammad, K. Butt, Z. Shah, Z. Mirza. Prescription and Dispensing Practices in Public Sector Health Facilities in Pakistan: Survey Report.
4. *J Pak Med Assoc* April 2004; Vol. 54, No. 4; 187-190.
5. Aragon SJ, Gesell SB. A patient satisfaction theory and its robustness across gender in emergency departments. A multi group structural equation modeling investigation. *Am J of Med Quality* 2003; 18:229-40.
6. Talluru Sreenivas, G. Prasad. Patient satisfaction A comparative study. *Journal of Academy of hospital administration* 2003; Vol 15, No.2-07-12.
7. Likert, R. (1932). A Technique for the Measurement of Attitudes, *Archives of Psychology*, 1993. No.140 :5-55
8. Kumari R, Idris MZ, Bhushan V, Khanna A, Agarwal M, Singh SK. Study on Patient Satisfaction in the
9. Government Allopathic Health Facilities of Lucknow District, India. *Indian J Community Med*, 2009; 34(1): 35-42.
10. McKinley RK, Roberts C. Patient's Satisfaction with out of hours primary medical care. *Qual Health Care* 2001; 10:23-8

11. World Health Organization. The World Health Report 2000- Health Systems: Improving Performance. Geneva: WHO, 2000.
12. Rao KD, Peters DH, Bandeen-Roche K. Towards patient-centered health services in India- a scale to measure patient perceptions of quality. *Int J Qual Health Care* 2006; 18:414-21
13. Boyer L, Francois P, Doutre E, Weil G, Labarere J. Perception and use of the results of patient satisfaction surveys by care providers in a French Teaching Hospital. *Int J Qual Health Care* 2006; 18:359-64.
14. Shaikh BT. Quality of health care: an absolute necessity for patient satisfaction. *J Pak Med Assoc* 2005; 55(11): 514-16.
15. Danish KF, Chaudhry MT, Khan UA, Naseer M. Patient Satisfaction An Experience at Islamic International Medical College / Railway Hospital. *JRMC* 2008;12(1):47-50
16. AartiVerma, R. K. Sarma. Evaluation of the exit proformas in use at special wards of public sector tertiary care center. *Journal of Academy of hospital administration* 2000; Vol 12, No.1
17. Arpitabh Attacharya, Prema Menon , Vipin K, KLN Rao. Study of patient satisfaction in a Tertiary referral hospital. *Journal of Academy of hospital administration* 2003; Vol 15, No. 1
18. Andrabi Syed Arshad, Hamid Shamila, Rohul, Jabeen, Anjum Fazli. Measuring patient satisfaction: A cross sectional study to improve quality of care at a tertiary care hospital. *Healthline*. January-June 2012 Volume 3 Issue 1; 59-62
19. Akoijam BS, Konjengbam S, Bishwalata R, Singh TA. Patients' Satisfaction with Hospital Care in a Referral Institute in Manipur. *Indian Journal of Public Health* October-December, 2007; Vol.51 No.4; 240-43